

A New Synthesis of Quinazolines. Part III. Synthesis of 3:4-Quinazoloneylquinazolines.

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In Parts I and II of this investigation it has been established that when ethyl carbamate condenses with acylamines, 4-oxyquinazolines are formed. In Part II of this investigation we found evidence of the methylation products of these bodies to have an *N*-methyl structure, although the parent quinazolines were amphoteric substances dissolving with equal readiness in acids and alkalis. Therefore it was reasonable to suppose that an equilibrium existed between the two forms, and this can be represented as in the following typical case:—

Asahina, Manske and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **131**, 1708) in their synthesis of rutaecarpin effected a condensation between a body containing the group —CO·NH— and anthranilic acid by means of phosphorous trichloride by the method of Sen and Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 646) and encountered no difficulty in synthesising a quinazolone. Therefore it seemed possible to fuse a further quinazoline ring to the substance II in the position 3:4, if it really assumes this structure in its tautomerism. To test this point we condensed 2-phenyl-4-oxyquinazoline (*cf.* Bhattacharya, Bose and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 297) with anthranilic

acid and we were able to isolate a product which clearly has the constitution (III).

III.

IV.

This substance (III) is, therefore, a 3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline. The physiological activity of rutaecarpin is partly due to the presence of a quinazoline ring-system in the molecule; therefore it seemed of interest to synthesise these bodies with two such fused rings in the molecules. Further interest in these compounds lies in the fact that these bodies may be looked upon as analogous to oxyberberine (IV) in which two *N*-atoms in position 1 and 1' of the former are replaced by two carbon atoms in the latter. Since it is quite common to find such replacement in natural products, therefore it is not unlikely that probably substances derived from (III) will ultimately be found in nature and therefore we place on record our observations as to the colour reactions of these substances in the experimental part. It is worthy of note that the colour reactions given by these substances are very similar to that of the alkaloid rutaecarpin but not of oxyberberine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of 2-Phenyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Phenyl-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline (Formula III, R=C₆H₅).

A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (1 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c.c.) was heated under reflux in a distillation flask for four hours. The excess of phosphorus trichloride was then removed by distillation. The residue was decomposed with ice. The solid collected and heated on the water-bath with 50 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (1:1) and the solution filtered. Unchanged starting material was recovered from the solution. The brown residue crystallised from absolute alcohol in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 241-242°. Yield, 0.3 gm. (Found: C, 77.69; H, 4.25; N, 13.05. C₂₁H₁₃ON₃ requires C, 78.01; H, 4.02; N, 13.00 per cent.).

The colourless solution of the substance in acetic acid exhibits a slight bluish-green fluorescence after introduction of a few drops of sulphuric acid. The faint yellow solution in sulphuric acid becomes brownish on the addition of Mandeline's reagent which on standing turns yellowish green. The hot alcoholic solution becomes light yellow on the addition of solid caustic potash but after dilution with water the colour is discharged. A solution of the substance in 50% sulphuric acid and a trace of nitric acid remains unchanged on dilution (*cf.* oxyberberine).

Condensation of 2:7-Dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2:7-Dimethyl-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

A mixture of 2:7-dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (2 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c.c.) was refluxed on the water-bath for four hours. After the removal of the excess of phosphorus trichloride, the residue was decomposed with ice and ground with 50 c.c. of cold hydrochloric acid (1:1). The free quinazoline (starting substance) was recovered from the solution. The brown residue crystallised in yellow needles from absolute alcohol; m.p. above 285°. Yield, 0.3 gm. (Found: N, 15.31. C₁₇H₁₃ON₃ requires N, 15.27 per cent.).

The substance exhibits the bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, gives a brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and light yellow colour with caustic potash in hot alcoholic solution as above but not the reaction of oxyberberine.

Condensation of 2-Methyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Methyl-6-methoxy-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

A mixture of 2-methyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (2 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.) was heated under reflux for four hours. The dark brown residue, after usual treatment, was crystallised from absolute alcohol in yellowish-brown needles, m. p. 240°; yield, 0.15 gm. (Found: N, 14.19. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.43 per cent.).

The substance gives the usual bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, a pale brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and a light yellow colour with caustic potash in hot alcoholic solution.

Condensation of 2-Benzyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Benzyl-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.
(Formula III, $R = C_6H_5 \cdot CH_2$)

2-Benzyl-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (1 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.) were thoroughly mixed and refluxed for four hours. After removal of the excess of phosphorus trichloride, the solid was decomposed with ice and heated on the water-bath with 50 c. c. of hydrochloric acid (1:1). The brownish-yellow product, on crystallisation from absolute alcohol, gave long, colourless, thin needles, m. p. 243-244°; yield, 0.25 gm. (Found: N, 12.40. $C_{22}H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 12.46 per cent.).

It gives the bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, a brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and a light yellow colour with caustic potash in hot alcoholic solution.

Condensation of 2-Benzyl-7-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Benzyl-7-methyl-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

A mixture of 2-benzyl-7-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (1 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.) was refluxed for four hours. The yellowish brown product obtained after removal of the excess of phosphorus trichloride and heating on the water-bath with 50 c. c. of hydrochloric acid (1:1) was crystallised from absolute alcohol in pale white needles, m. p. 213°; yield, 0.2 gm. (Found: N, 11.81. $C_{23}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 11.96 per cent.).

The substance gives slight bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, a brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and the usual light yellow colour with caustic potash in alcoholic solution.

Condensation of 2-Benzyl-6-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Benzyl-6-methyl-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

The quinazoline (1 g.) was thoroughly mixed with anthranilic acid (1 g.) and refluxed with phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.) for four hours. The product after usual treatment was heated on the water-bath with 50 c. c. of hydrochloric acid (1:1) and filtered. The brownish-yellow solid on crystallisation from alcohol gave colourless plates, m. p. 235—236°; yield, 0.25 gm. (Found: N; 12.13. $C_{23}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 11.96 per cent.).

The substance gives only slight bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, brown colour with Mandeline's reagent and a bright yellow colour with caustic potash in hot alcoholic solution.

Condensation of 2-Benzyl-8-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Benzyl-8-methoxy-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

The oxyquinazoline (1 g.) and anthranilic acid (1 g.) were thoroughly mixed and refluxed with phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.). The product was isolated as usual. On crystallisation from absolute alcohol, colourless plates were obtained; m. p. 254°; yield, 0.2 gm. (Found: N, 11.41. $C_{23}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.44 per cent.).

It exhibits slight bluish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, a brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and a yellow colour with caustic potash in alcoholic solution.

Condensation of 2-Benzyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 2-Benzyl-6-methoxy-3:4-quinazoloneylquinazoline.

A mixture of 2-benzyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline (1 g.), anthranilic acid (1 g.) and phosphorus trichloride (10 c. c.) was refluxed for four hours. The brownish-yellow product, obtained after isolation in the usual way, gave white plates on crystallising from alcohol,

m. p. 244°. Yield, 0.2 gm. (Found: N, 11.31. $C_{23}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.44 per cent.).

A slight yellowish-green fluorescence with acetic acid and a drop of sulphuric acid, a brownish colour with Mandeline's reagent and a yellow colour with caustic potash in hot alcoholic solution are exhibited by the substance.

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